

On a Simplified, Biophysical Model for Hair-Bundle Dynamics

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Abstract. Biophysical models describing auditory systems typically include nonlinear differential equations with ample free parameters. Some parameters can be fixed through experimental measurements, but those describing internal cellular processes frequently remain inaccessible. Thus, auditory models often have too many free parameters, limiting their predictive power. We derive a five-variable model for the active, mechanical motility of auditory hair cells. With this model, we rank free parameters by their influence on the model's core features. Furthermore, we fix the least influential parameters, yielding a five-parameter model with refined predictive power. As a result, we determine the most influential parameters, illuminating the key biophysical elements of the cell.

INTRODUCTION

To describe hair-bundle dynamics, models of various parameter and variable counts have been developed [1, 2, 3, 4]. With each refinement, the models have acquired additional equations to describe the hair cell's internal mechanisms. The models, hence, suffer from a proliferation of parameters. While measurements can constrain or approximate some of these parameters, many are not experimentally accessible and must, justly, be treated as free parameters.

We construct a reduced, biophysically motivated model for hair-bundle motion. We start with a comprehensive theoretical model of hair-bundle dynamics, garnered from prior literature, to describe the hair cell's internal processes. Next, we simplify it algebraically to produce a nondimensional version of the full biophysical model. We select several key features of the simulation and rank the full set of parameters by their influence on these. Because this ranking provides a quantitative assessment of relative influence, justified by well-studied statistical analyses, we fix the less influential ones. Finally, we compare the resultant reduced model to experimental measurements (see Fig. 1 for overview of our procedure).

FIGURE 1. General procedure used for model reduction. Red nodes indicate start (ellipse and curved parallelogram) or end (pill shape) nodes. Blue nodes (rectangle) indicate actions. Green nodes (rhombus) indicate decisions.

	Quantity	Significance	Equation
Variable	\tilde{x}_{hb}	Hair-bundle position	$\tilde{\tau}_{hb}\dot{\tilde{x}}_{hb} = -(\tilde{F}_{gs} + \tilde{x}_{hb})$
	\tilde{x}_a	Myosin-motor position	$\dot{\tilde{x}}_a = \tilde{S}_{max}\tilde{S}(\tilde{F}_{gs} - \tilde{x}_a) - (1 - \tilde{S}_{max})\tilde{C}$
	p_m	Ca ²⁺ -binding probability for motor	$\tilde{\tau}_m\dot{p}_m = \tilde{C}_m p_T(1 - p_m) - p_m$
	p_{gs}	Ca ²⁺ -binding probability for gating spring	$\tilde{\tau}_{gs}\dot{p}_{gs} = \tilde{C}_{gs} p_T(1 - p_{gs}) - p_{gs}$
	p_T	Open probability for MET channel	$\tilde{\tau}_T\dot{p}_T = p_T(\infty) - p_T$
Function	\tilde{k}_{gs}	Rescaled gating-spring stiffness	$\tilde{k}_{gs} = 1 - p_{gs}(1 - \tilde{k}_{gs,min})$
	\tilde{x}_{gs}	Effective stretch distance for forces	$\tilde{x}_{gs} = \tilde{\chi}_{gs}\tilde{x}_{gs} - \tilde{\chi}_a\tilde{x}_a + \tilde{x}_c$
	\tilde{F}_{gs}	Effective force (gating/extent springs, pivot)	$\tilde{F}_{gs} = \tilde{k}_{gs}(\tilde{x}_{gs} - p_T)$
	\tilde{C}	Climbing rate for motor	$\tilde{C} = 1 - p_m(1 - \tilde{C}_{min})$
	\tilde{S}	Slipping rate for motor	$\tilde{S} = \tilde{S}_{min} - p_m(1 - \tilde{S}_{min})$
	$p_T(\infty)$	Steady-state probability for transduction channel	$\left[1 + \exp\left(\tilde{U}_{gs,max}\left(\Delta\tilde{E}^\varnothing - \tilde{k}_{gs}(\tilde{x}_{gs} - \frac{1}{2})\right)\right)\right]^{-1}$

TABLE 1. Variables and functions in the nondimensional model. For each quantity, the ‘‘Significance’’ column indicates its physical significance, and the ‘‘Equation’’ column shows its defining equation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparing the Biological System

As our biological system, we studied the sacculus from the North American bullfrog (*Rana catesbeiana*). The amphibian sacculus has been used extensively for experiments on hair-bundle mechanics [5, 6]. In the dissected sacculi, we bathed the hair cells in artificial solutions that mimicked their natural fluid environment. We dissected sacculi from three different frogs, attaining retrieve three total datasets. Finally, we optically tracked the position of the hair bundles *ex vivo*.

We collected recordings using an upright optical microscope with a water-immersion objective. This microscope was mounted on an optical table and placed inside an acoustically isolated chamber. We obtained 16-bit TIFF images with a resolution of 108.3 nm px⁻¹ at 1000 frames per second. For each frame, we determined the mean bundle position weighted by pixel intensity (see Fig. 2). These positions yielded traces of active hair-bundle oscillations, allowing direct comparison to numerical simulations.

Deriving the Biophysical Model

Our model incorporates various biophysical features gleaned from previous theoretical studies [2, 3, 7, 8], aiming for a comprehensive description of hair-bundle mechanics. Prior work has demonstrated that the biophysical model accurately and reliably reproduces the experimental observations.

To simplify our parameter-reduction approach, we first algebraically convert the full system of dimensional ODEs into nondimensional form. Apart from reducing the number of free parameters, this simplified form also elucidates the main dynamics underlying hair-bundle mechanics. We signify nondimensionalized quantities with a tilde ($\tilde{}$). This model is shown in Table 1.

N_p	Parameter	Value	Significance
15	—	—	All mechanisms included
14	\tilde{C}_{min}	1	Constant climbing rate
13	$\tilde{\tau}_T$	0	Equilibrium transduction-channel dynamics
12	$\tilde{\tau}_{gs}$	1	Moderate calcium-feedback time constant for gating spring
11	\tilde{C}_m	1	Moderate calcium-feedback strength at motors
10	\tilde{x}_c	0	Null gating-spring offset
9	$\tilde{\chi}_{hb}$	1	Moderate coupling from stereocilia on gating-spring force
8	\tilde{S}_{min}	0	Maximal variability for slipping rate
7	\tilde{C}_{gs}	1000	Strong calcium-feedback strength on gating spring
6	$\tilde{\tau}_{hb}$	1	Moderate stereocilia time constant
5	\tilde{S}_{max}	0.5	Equal effective slipping and climbing rates
4	$\tilde{U}_{gs,max}$	10	Elastic potential energy of gating spring
3	$\tilde{\chi}_a$	1	Coupling from motors on gating-spring force
2	$\tilde{k}_{gs,min}$	1	Variability of gating-spring stiffness
1	$\tilde{\tau}_m$	10	Calcium-feedback time constant for motor
0	$\Delta\tilde{E}^\emptyset$	1	Free energy of transduction-channel opening

TABLE 2. Parameters in the nondimensional model, ranked from least to most influential (top to bottom). N_p represents the number of free parameters in the model (derived in Table 1) after fixing the adjacent parameter at the corresponding fixed value. Parameters were fixed cumulatively such that all in the above rows remained fixed. The ‘‘Significance’’ column indicates the physical significance 1) of fixing the corresponding parameter for fixed parameters or 2) of the corresponding biophysical mechanism for unfixed parameters. When fixed, the unfixed parameters produced simulations with a lower-quality fit (see Fig. 2).

Obtaining the Parameter Ranking

We ranked the importance of each free parameter in the model, quantified by its influence on the simulations. We began with the nondimensional model (shown in Table 1), which produces time-dependent traces of bundle position \tilde{x}_{hb} . We selected five prominent features, characterizing our limit cycles, to assess the influence of each parameter. We then ranked each free parameter by its influence on bundle dynamics, using statistical techniques from sensitivity analysis. We utilized two distinct sensitivity indices, namely total-effect (TE; [9]) and PAWN [10], so as to check our ranking through two independent approaches. From these rankings, we chose one final representative.

We characterized time-dependent traces of hair-bundle motion with the following five properties: 1) a Boolean quantity, which indicates whether a trace shows oscillatory motion, 2-4) mean, amplitude, and frequency, which characterize the oscillation’s size, and 5) skewness, which characterizes the oscillation’s shape.

We found the TE and PAWN indices for each combination of 15 parameters and five properties, $2 \times 15 \times 5 = 150$ indices in total. To calculate these indices, we used $\sim 500,000$ instances of the model distributed among a uniform, independent collection of random parameter samples [11]. Taking into account all 150 indices, we chose a single representative for our final parameter ranking (shown in Table 2).

Evaluating the Best-Fit Model

We reduced the parameter count in our full 15-parameter model, while improving the model’s predictive accuracy. We first used Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) to fit a collection of nondimensional models to an experimental dataset. These fits included steps to rescale amplitude and frequency of the model. We then incorporated two distinct information criteria, namely Akaike [12] and Bayesian [13], to choose the most predictive model.

We used MCMC to determine the maximum-likelihood (ML) parameter set of a model, given an experimental dataset. MCMC optimization yielded collections of parameters that accurately modeled the three datasets (see Fig. 2).

MCMC relies on a collection of random walkers to converge toward the maximum-likelihood estimator (MLE)

FIGURE 2. Comparison of best-fit models to three datasets along with information criteria. Each plot corresponds to a different dataset. Black points with gray error bars show dataset values, position (y-axis) vs. time (x-axis). Colored solid lines show best-fit models with varying numbers of parameters: $N_p = 4$ (orange), $N_p = 5$ (green), and $N_p = 6$ (blue). Inset: Three measures of fit quality vs. number of parameters N_p in the nondimensional model. From top to bottom, these lines show Bayesian (BIC) then Akaike (AIC) information criteria followed by a measure of maximum likelihood ($-\ln\hat{L}$). Vertical green lines indicate where $N_p = 5$.

[14]. Each walker performs its own fit to the model, attempting to converge toward the MLE, analogous to performing multiple gradient-descent fits simultaneously. However, unlike in gradient descent, these walkers stochastically “gravitate” toward each other, according to a predefined set of moves, making them mutually dependent.

We rescaled from nondimensional to dimensional bundle position by numerically fitting four characteristic values. These include scaling and offset of nondimensional bundle position $\tilde{x}_{hb}(\tilde{t})$; plus scaling and offset of nondimensional time \tilde{t} . We performed this rescaling operation as the last step in our fitting procedure, after the MCMC algorithm chose a parameter set.

Information criteria (ICs) estimate the prediction error of a model relative to a dataset [15]. They penalize large numbers of degrees of freedom, thus favoring fewer free parameters and reducing the chances of overfitting. They also favor large maximum likelihood \hat{L} , thus lessening the chances of underfitting. A smaller IC indicates that a model has a smaller prediction error. Hence, models with lesser ICs yield preferable fits to experimental results.

DISCUSSION

We applied quantitative methods to assess and rank the importance of free parameters, permitting us to fix the less influential ones. We thus reduced this biophysical model to have only five parameters, while still reproducing recordings of spontaneous hair-bundle oscillations (shown in Fig. 2) To demonstrate our methods on a concrete example, we modeled the motion of hair cells.

Our parameter-reduction methods yield insight into the model’s internal cellular processes. Each biophysical process and element corresponds to a set of model parameters and explains some observable behavior. Therefore, by identifying the most influential parameters, we can determine which internal elements most impact the observed bundle movement.

We developed comprehensive statistical and computational methods to reduce the number of free parameters in a model (outlined in Fig. 1). We first derived a 15-parameter, nondimensional, biophysical model (in Table 1). We then established five representative model properties. For each property, we quantified parameter influences by computing their TE and PAWN indices. Finally, we iteratively fixed the least influential parameters (at values shown in Table 2), until we minimized the Akaike and Bayesian information criteria, obtaining an accurate and predictive fit (shown in Fig. 2). As a final result, we acquired an accurate five-parameter model for spontaneous hair-bundle oscillations.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Morgan, Thienpont]: Very interesting topic, and mostly it's very clear.

- For me personally it might be useful to have a figure indicating parameters such as \tilde{x}_{hb} and \tilde{x}_a .
- In table 1: '*' indicates an unfixed parameter' and it's also in the table 'fixed' and 'unfixed'?
- Figure 2: For me it's not really clear what the difference is between the three datasets.
- Maybe it's also interesting to mention what the difference is between the Bayesian and Akaike information criteria.

[Joseph, Marcinik]: Thanks for the feedback, Morgan!

- We like this idea to have a figure indicating the parameters. We replace the blocks of equations with a table, making the model more understandable.
- The asterisk indicating unfixed is indeed redundant. We remove this from the table.
- Each of the three datasets comes from a different frog. We wanted to model many different types of oscillating traces. We clarify this in the methods section.

- We agree that the distinction between Akaike and Bayesian information criteria is interesting. However, we do not mention these differences in these proceedings because their differences are too intricate for a short proceedings. We contemplated whether to add the equations for these two information criteria, but they do not particularly help conceptualize them, so we decided not to include them.